

SECTION OF MATHEMATICS, PHYSICS, AND INFORMATICS

INTELLIGENT MODELS FOR DEMAND FORECASTING USING AI

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Abstract

This article examines modern demand forecasting methods using intelligent models, including machine learning (ML) algorithms, deep learning, and statistical time series models. The study analyzes the effectiveness of various approaches, such as neural networks, ensemble methods, and time series models (e.g., ARIMA and ARIMAX), in demand forecasting across different economic sectors. Based on real data analysis, the accuracy and applicability of the proposed models are assessed, highlighting the advantages and limitations of intelligent models compared to traditional forecasting methods.

Keywords: demand forecasting, intelligent models, machine learning (ML), deep learning, neural networks, clustering, supply chain, data analysis.

Introduction

Increasingly, successful supply chain and inventory management requires accurate demand forecasting. This relevance is especially evident against the global backdrop of fluctuating market demand and growing competition. Traditional forecasting methods, such as statistical models, are often limited in their ability to account for complex and multidimensional dependencies among demand-influencing factors. This can lead to under- or overestimations of future needs, negatively impacting business efficiency.

With advancements in artificial intelligence (AI), there is now the potential to implement more flexible and accurate models that consider a wide range of variables and dynamic market changes. Various AI-based forecasting models, such as neural networks (NN), machine learning (ML) methods, and deep learning (DL), demonstrate significant improvements in prediction accuracy. They are capable of enabling quick adjustments to shifts in consumer preferences and other external factors.

Intelligent models driven on AI open up new opportunities in demand forecasting. This approach provides companies with higher levels of accuracy and flexibility in decision-making. Such models enable the analysis of large volumes of data, uncover hidden dependencies, and deliver precise forecasts even in uncertain conditions. This helps companies manage inventory and supply chains more effectively, enhancing their adaptability to rapidly changing market conditions. The aim of this study is to examine intelligent models for demand forecasting and analyze their effectiveness compared to traditional methods. The article examines modern statistical time series models and ML and DL algorithms for demand forecasting. An assessment of the effectiveness of these approaches across various industries is conducted.

Main part. Analysis of effective models and AI-based algorithms for demand forecasting

Demand forecasting using AI methods requires careful selection of algorithms suited to the data volume and time constraints. Each algorithm has its unique capabilities, that make it applicable to various forecasting scenarios. A number of major models are currently used to determine various demand conditions.

Regression models are foundational in cases where the relationship between demand and its predictors is linear or close to it. In such scenarios, linear regression is commonly used to identify optimal weights for variables to predict target values, while polynomial regression is applied when data shows non-linear trends that can be approximated using polynomial functions. Ridge and Lasso regressions are variations of linear regression that help reduce overfitting, particularly in tasks with numerous features, adding regularization to improve model stability and make it less sensitive to data fluctuations.

Modern NN are powerful algorithms capable of detecting complex, multidimensional dependencies in data. They are particularly useful for time-series forecasting, where demand changes are driven by multiple factors. Multilayer perceptrons (MLP) represent the basic neural network architecture, suited for tasks without explicit sequence dependencies. Recurrent neural networks (RNN), on the other hand, are ideal for time-series data, as they capture sequential relationships by retaining information from previous steps. Enhanced RNN, such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks and Gated Recurrent Units (GRU), address the vanishing gradient problem and are suitable for long-term demand forecasting, as they capture dependencies over extended time spans. The backpropagation neural network (BPNN or BP) is a supervised learning algorithm widely used for training feedforward NN. It optimizes model performance by adjusting weights in the network through error minimization. This parameter is achieved by propagating the prediction error backward from the output layer to earlier layers [1].

Support Vector Machines (SVM) are used in tasks where it is essential to segment data into distinct classes and define boundaries that best separate these classes. While SVM are frequently applied in classification, they are also effective for regression tasks if data needs to be segmented based on certain attributes. Support Vector Regression (SVR), for instance, focuses on minimizing deviations between predicted and actual values. It makes this algorithm useful for small datasets with linear or slightly non-linear relationships.

Ensemble methods, such as **Random Forest (RF)** and **Gradient Boosting (GB)**, have proven highly effective for demand forecasting. They combine multiple

«weak» models to achieve a more accurate outcome [2]. Random Forest uses an ensemble of decision trees, each created using a random sample of data and features, and produces a final prediction by averaging the results across trees. This approach increases robustness against outliers and reduces overfitting. Gradient Boosting builds models by sequentially adding trees that correct errors of previous ones. Libraries such as XGBoost, LightGBM, and CatBoost offer gradient boosting implementations tailored to different data types and forecasting tasks.

Although **clustering** is not inherently a forecasting method, it plays a significant role in data preparation for AI models. Algorithms like k-means or hierarchical clustering allow grouping data with similar characteristics, enabling the development of separate forecasting models for each group, which often improves the overall model accuracy.

Time series models are also widely used for demand forecasting when there is a strong temporal dependency. Among these models, ARIMA and its extension, ARIMAX, are particularly effective. **ARIMA (AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average)** model is based on three components: autoregression, integration, and moving average. It is suitable for tasks where demand exhibits a stable temporal structure, such as trends and seasonal fluctuations [3]. The model is represented as ARIMA(p, d, q), where:

- p – the order of autoregression (number of time lags),
- d – the degree of differencing needed to remove the trend,
- q – the order of the moving average (incorporating prediction errors).

This model is most effective when the time series is stationary, meaning that data has been transformed to eliminate trends. This makes it ideal for forecasts where

past values and autocorrelation are important factors. It is particularly useful for data with pronounced seasonal patterns and predictable trends.

ARIMAX (AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average with Exogenous Variables) is an extended version of ARIMA. It includes exogenous variables and additional external factors that can influence the forecast. In demand forecasting, ARIMAX can incorporate factors like economic indicators, price data, or marketing campaigns if they significantly impact demand. This model is also represented as ARIMA (p, d, q), but it includes exogenous variables, which enhances forecasting accuracy under the influence of external factors. It becomes especially effective when forecasting depends not only on the time-based structure of the data but also on external events affecting demand. This model combines time lags with values of external factors, making it a flexible tool for data analysis across various industries.

These algorithms can be used individually or in combination. Each case of the AI-based model implementation can depend on the task specifics and available data. Selecting an algorithm that best fits the business needs and data type becomes essential for achieving high forecasting accuracy.

Analysis of the effectiveness of intelligent models and their application across various sectors

Intelligent models vary widely in terms of accuracy and applicability depending on the industry and specific forecasting requirements. Traditional time-series models may perform well in cases with clear, consistent trends and are effective for industries with strong seasonal demand. Algorithms powered by ML provide higher accuracy in industries where demand patterns are highly variable and influenced by multiple external factors [4]. Many studies have been recently conducted that are aimed at analyzing various models in the field of demand forecasting (table 1).

Table 1.

Forecasting demand studies on statistical and AI models [5-8]

Objective	Methodology used	Outcome
Demand forecasting model for the hospitality industry, predicting weekly hotel demand four weeks in advance using an Attention-LSTM approach.	K-means Clustering, Hotel Embedding, Attention-LSTM, Seq2One, Spectral Clustering, RF Regressor, GB Regressor, Extra Trees Regressor, XGBoost, Regressor, Gated Recurrent Unit.	LSTM model that uses feature embeddings outperforms other models, achieving up to 29% improvement in mean absolute error.
A flexible hybrid ML model designed to improve load prediction accuracy with lower computational demands, particularly in the context of smart grids and demand-side management.	The combined use of CNN, LSTM, and MLP models enables a comprehensive approach, leveraging CNN for feature extraction, LSTM for capturing temporal dependencies, and MLP for final decision-making, enhancing overall model performance.	Demand forecasting with Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) of 1,71% for 30-min predictions, 3,5% for 1-day predictions, and 5,1% for 1-week predictions.
Demand forecasting techniques for a retail chain, comparing five ML regression models.	RF, XGBoost, AdaBoost, and ANN, with a proposed hybrid model (RF-XGBoost-LR).	The hybrid model outperformed individual models in forecasting accuracy. The model explains 95,51% of the data and variables incorporated.
Application of ML to cluster hotel booking curves for hotel demand forecasting.	Clustering Booking Curves, Additive pickup method.	A DL model performed better than time series (ARIMA), econometric (Vector Autoregression), and other LSTM models.

As it was shown above, high accuracy can be achieved by combining statistical and intelligent ML and DL models. Energy companies use these techniques to predict demand for electricity and fuel. Various NN and ARIMA models help in forecasting daily and seasonal demand, as it enables efficient energy distribution. These models can incorporate weather patterns, economic indicators, and consumer behavior. It helps to balance supply with fluctuating demand and optimize energy production. The 2023 study focused on

demand forecasting for new energy vehicles using a SARIMA-LSTM-BP hybrid model within an intelligent supply chain framework [9]. The model demonstrated superior accuracy and achieved lower root mean squared error (RMSE) and other values compared to traditional models like LSTM and BP. This innovative approach highlights the effectiveness of combining statistical and DL techniques for improved demand forecasting in the new energy industry (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Comparison of the RMSE values for the different prediction models.

Intelligent models have shown significant effectiveness across various industries. They offer powerful tools for improving demand forecasting and decision-making. While ARIMA and ARIMAX models excel in structured, stationary data environments, ML and DL models are generally more adaptable and can achieve greater accuracy with large, complex datasets.

Conclusion

The integration of intelligent models based on AI-technologies offers significant advancements in demand forecasting accuracy. Traditional methods often fall short in accounting for the complex and dynamic variables influencing demand. Innovative AI-driven approaches bring a level of flexibility and precision that supports more effective supply chain and inventory management. Leveraging historical data and adapting to real-time shifts, these models give companies a competitive advantage. It enables organizations to react quickly to changes in consumer behavior and external drivers. Intelligent demand forecasting models will become an indispensable tool for optimizing decision-making in rapidly changing market environments as AI technologies continue to evolve.

References

1. Sun W, Tan B, Wang Q. Multi-step wind speed forecasting based on secondary decomposition algorithm and optimized back propagation neural network. *Applied Soft Computing*. 2021;113:107894.
2. Punia S, Nikolopoulos K, Singh SP, Madaan JK, Litsiou K. Deep learning with long short-term

memory networks and random forests for demand forecasting in multi-channel retail. *International journal of production research*. 2020;58(16):4964-79.

3. Kontopoulou VI, Panagopoulos AD, Kakkos I, Matsopoulos GK. A review of ARIMA vs. machine learning approaches for time series forecasting in data driven networks. *Future Internet*. 2023;15(8):255.

4. Korostin O. Analysis of AI effectiveness in reducing human errors in processing transportation requests. *German International Journal of Modern Science*. 2024;88:66-69.

5. Kaya K, Yılmaz Y, Yaslan Y, Ögüdücü ŞG, Çıngı F. Demand forecasting model using hotel clustering findings for hospitality industry. *Information Processing & Management*. 2022;59(1):102816.

6. Taleb I, Guerard G, Fauberteau F, Nguyen N. A flexible deep learning method for energy forecasting. *Energies*. 2022;15(11):3926.

7. Mitra A, Jain A, Kishore A, Kumar P. A comparative study of demand forecasting models for a multi-channel retail company: a novel hybrid machine learning approach. *Operations research forum*. 2022;3(4):58. Cham: Springer International Publishing.

8. Viverit L, Heo CY, Pereira LN, Tiana G. Application of machine learning to cluster hotel booking curves for hotel demand forecasting. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*. 2023;111:103455.

9. Ma X, Li M, Tong J, Feng X. Deep learning combinatorial models for intelligent supply chain demand forecasting. *Biomimetics*. 2023;8(3):312.